

SOME ASPECTS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN NAMANGAN REGION

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INTRODUCTION

Today's in the day in Uzbekistan local himself himself manage organs in his life small business and private entrepreneurship of the field development to himself special place is holding That's why of the neighborhood small business and entrepreneurship subjects with breathless be the work take to go this of structure small business and entrepreneurship development research in reaching important place holds After all, in Uzbekistan small business and private entrepreneurship his own long to the past have from long ago our people marriage in the style of property ownership make it sell and disposition reach marriage of our style structural part being came Only soviet system rule did only during of the state private property relatively take went reverse policy as a result entrepreneurship basics was forgotten and own essence lost But in the 90s of the 20th century

ABSTRACT

In the article of Uzbekistan Namangan regions in their neighborhoods small business and entrepreneurship development some aspects in particular word is conducted. In independence years this in the regions in the field done being increased reforms results, achievements and problems historical in aspect analysis done.

heads, more precisely by doing in other words, Uzbekistan independence threshold and from the first years of independence considering this of the field again recovery and development for wide opportunities was created. Private property ownership to do feeling, entrepreneurship skills form started And this them additional property work take out, add income get desire to the body come started showed. In the XXI century in Uzbekistan market economy passing relationship with economy and people of the farm all field in networks public privatization for wide chance created, private property and entrepreneurs interests obstacle divisor all restrictions take thrown away In this period basically open type shareholding societies activities expansion, businesses shares to entrepreneurs auctions through sale, public privatization and small of business role increase for valuable pieces of paper the market to form attention was

directed. In this regard republic regions, especially neighborhoods to himself special sociodemographic condition, natural climate condition and geographical from the location come out of this in the regions small business and private entrepreneurship fields to develop serious attention was directed. That 's it regions in line of Uzbekistan southern regions the so-called Namangan region separately cause transition can this

regions in their neighborhoods from time immemorial family entrepreneurship and household development to himself special ethno-regional features there is being, in this basically carpet making confectionery, knitting and construction products work release, wool and Karakol skin products work production, woodworking, furniture making, jewelry, embroidery fields developed this fields development new to stage on the rise undoubtedly.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The size of the main indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship in economic sectors in Namangan region

Years	Industry (billion soums)	Construction (billion soums)	Employment (thousand people)	Export (million USD)	Import (million USD)	Trade (billion soums)	Agriculture, forestry and fisheries (billion soums)	Service (billion soums)	Shipping (million tons)	Freight turnover (mln. ton-km)
2019	5002.7	3310.1	916.7	291.2	529.0	8685.2	16424.5	5176.4	24.1	519.1
2020	5471.3	4101.3	884.3	195.3	376.4	10422.4	18798.7	5842.3	24.3	539.7
2021	7174.3	5247.9	991.9	253.5	474.6	14216.3	22671.5	11786.8	27.2	583.3

Independence years in history small business by being created gross internal product in the composition small enterprise and micro firms share significant level increased that he went attention deserves. This is it in the regions work resources enough although it is natural condition and geographical to the location according to raw material resources somewhat scarce that shows . But in the field take going reforms and of work practical the result analysis to do

based on so reasoning appear In our opinion, it is entrepreneurship with engaged in legal and physical to individuals state only one in the law shown without known rights to give enough not maybe that 's it right and from guarantees full use for conditions to create is more important or entrepreneurs promotion, product quality improve and from multiplication interest increase, healthy competition environment to the body bring, state monopoly check put etc gives the expected

effect. With that together of independence new during in the region small business and entrepreneurship in the fields grow trends not so much that it was not observed let's see can For example, for 2020 come industry product work issue Namangan 1003.2 bln. This is special note reach entrepreneurship is necessary important direction has been family entrepreneurship field in the region somewhat good developed This is a family neighborhood cooperation main place holds For example, today in the day republic in their neighborhoods family entrepreneurship and household with engaged in,own work in return work issued products local and the world to the markets take coming out entrepreneurs the majority organize is enough of course family entrepreneurship and of household development as a result of both to himself in the region special tradition formed attention in the future this fields development separately attention focus important is. This in the region from time immemorial traditional people craftsmanship types separately attention directed confirms. In this regard to numbers appeal if done, indeed, in Uzbekistan neighborhoods by family entrepreneurship to support separately attention is being directed. For this purpose republic association organize done division,13 departments, 153 departments across the Republic activity showed. In this place small business and entrepreneurship to the fields foreign of investments attraction of the industry development effect doer of the factors that note reach it is necessary Now foreign investments entrepreneurship to the fields attraction to be done regions in the section situation more it becomes clear. Historical to

research see,abroad investments attraction to do according to of the republic different in the regions condition known disproportions and gradations at the expense of is different . For example,in Namangan region,which we are studying last twenty year inside this indicator from 0.1% to 22 % grew up Exactly this one the indicator remained at 5.3-6.8% in Namangan region . That is this indicator yet this also known about problems of existence is evidence . For example, 2021 in Namangan region entrepreneurship subjects the number is 54.8 thousand organize reached their the number year 17 percent during o' scan . In this regard entrepreneurship development for construction materials,tourism,village economy,local industry such as in the fields have reserves . Including the industry development cotton textile fruits and vegetables cultivation and again work,construction materials work release directions big opportunities there is But the region in their neighborhoods in the field done increased affairs in line problem and there are also disadvantages . In particular,large industry potential have of imported goods in the region share high level preserved the rest Internal of the market local to products the need not studied. Ready clothing,leather production issuer enterprises of possibilities efficient use to the road not placed . Demand is high was local products with region internal the market is low provided . Gypsum board,various different Corrugated cardboard, one once dishes,paper packages,construction and village economy techniques integral parts,teeth washing paste and shampoo,nail products work issuer entrepreneurship subjects there is not Services in the field of 758 repairs,

1,078 veterinary service and meat shops, 1,214 bathrooms and shoes sewing (repair) service, 1,319 chemicals cleaning and household equipment repair, 938 hairdressers and beauty salons services population in the middle need to be regardless to areas entrepreneurship subjects attraction not done It is obvious proof as here is one how many year -old "Business indicator" system of regions business rating work comes out Rating in places entrepreneurship for created conditions evaluates. In the assessment entrepreneurs directly participation enough.

CONCLUSION

In general, take went studies Namangan region in their neighborhoods small business and private entrepreneurship wide development for comfortable entrepreneurship environment create, service to show fields progressive carry on main to the task turning around that it is going confirmed. And this in the region in business different benefits formed and the population needy the layers are also from it enjoy be started This fields with the help of country the field progressive in progress to himself special

experience that he collected showed. But small business and entrepreneurship subjects to the activity state offices (commercial bank, insurance companies, tax offices, district and city administrations, the state management authorities, officials persons and etc.) resources distribution and the price designation to the process and another to activities intervention issues efficient to changes lack of achievement in the field to himself special problems the existence of them eliminate reach on the surface series measures to see necessity confirming. Taken away research results and historical analyses based on in our opinion, entrepreneurship development for the following important aspects attention focus: first, small business and entrepreneurship formation for necessary a must conditions create an area quality in terms of new to stage take output ; - secondly, the state property objects sell process acceleration through through valuable papers and shares trade to turnover wide attraction do, and this funds income enterprises equipment and personnel again preparation to work attraction to be done necessary.

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